

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.2
Comparazione grafica
dei risultati

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 2.2
Grafična primerjava
rezultatov

NOVEMBER 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Dudine A.⁽²⁾, Menegon D.⁽²⁾, Gostič S.⁽³⁾, Gams M.⁽⁴⁾

(1) Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Trieste (Italy)

(2) Fibre Net Spa, Pavia di Udine (Italy)

(3) ZRMK, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

www.ita-slo.eu/pro-sis

<https://www.facebook.com/61556327101140>

<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/interreg-italia-slovenija-pro-sis>

PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.2 Graphic comparison of the results

NOVEMBER 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Dudine A.⁽²⁾, Menegon D.⁽²⁾,
Gostič S.⁽³⁾, Gams M.⁽⁴⁾

(1) Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Trieste (Italy)

(2) Fibre Net Spa, Pavia di Udine (Italy)

(3) ZRMK, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

www.ita-slo.eu/pro-sis

<https://www.facebook.com/61556327101140>

<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/interreg-italia-slovenija-pro-sis>

Report 2.2

Graphic comparison of the results

Summary

1. Introduction	2
2. Comparisons of simplified numerical simulations.....	3
2.1. Portal frames.....	4
2.2. Single story walls	14
2.3. Two story walls.....	24
2.4. Pilot building.....	29
2.5. Benchmark building	32
3. Comparisons with simplified analytical models	39
3.1. Portal frames.....	40
3.2. Single story walls	49
3.3. Two-story walls	59
4. Comparisons with detail numerical models	63
Acknowledgments	66
References	66

1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 2.2 of the PRO-SIS project, titled “Graphical representation of the results of WP2.1 and critical discussion”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In the previous REPORT 1.4: “Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation program” [1] the procedures to be used in some common commercial software for analysing the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings, taking into account the effects of reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques are described.

In the previous REPORT 2.1: “Results of the analyses on various existing masonry buildings with the procedures of WP1” [2], a series of benchmark examples of individual structural elements (piers and spandrels), portal frames, single- and double-story walls and entire buildings are analysed independently, by using the different software.

In this REPORT 2.2, the results obtained with the different software are gathered and compared, to assess the reliability of the simulations; both unreinforced and strengthened masonry configurations are analysed and compared. To further support this objective, additional comparisons are made between the obtained results and those derived from simplified analytical methods, which were calibrated using experimental data from the CONSTRAIN project (discussed in Report 1.1 [3]), as well as advanced numerical modelling methods (REPORTS 1.2 [4] and 1.3 [5]).

2. Comparisons of simplified numerical simulations

In this section, the capacity curves obtained in REPORT 2.1 [2] from the pushover analysis by using four different software (Midas GEN, 3Muri, PRO-SAP and SREMB) are reported.

The capacity curves plot the total base shear against the lateral displacement. The graphs collect results for unreinforced masonry (**URM**), masonry reinforced on one side (**R1**) and on two sides (**R2**).

The colours in the graph represent the different software: Midas GEN (**green dashed line**), PRO-SAP (**blue solid line**), 3Muri (**yellow solid line**) and SREMB (**pink dashed line**).

In each sub-section, the main geometrical characteristics of the analysed configurations are summarized; for further details, refer to Report 2.1 [2].

2.1. Portal frames

A portal frame representing a symmetric wall with a door opening in the middle is analysed; the main features are summarized in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 Portal frame (measures in mm)

The results are gathered in three different tables, provided in the following, which differ in the magnitude of the axial load applied to the piers (0.1-0.3-0.5 MPa). In each table, the curves on the left refer to the configuration without horizontal tie (t_0), and those on the right with tie (t_1). Only the Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.0 was analysed with the SREMB software.

Clearly, the higher resistance of the URM spandrels in t_1 configurations allows for a better exploitation of the piers' lateral performance, than in t_0 cases. However, the impact of the tie is greatly mitigated in the R1-R2 configurations, as the CRM provides the spandrel with an effective coupling effect for the piers.

It is worth to remember that, for the t_0 configurations, the Midas Gen simulations assume for the URM spandrels an elastic-brittle-residual plastic behaviour; differently, the PRO-SAP and 3Muri simulations assume an elastic-plastic behaviour by inserting a fictitious horizontal tie resistance corresponding to the expected resistance. In SREMB, there is no difference between t_0 and t_1 , due to the cantilever behaviour assumption for the piers. The differences among the models results however mitigated as the axial load increases.

Considering the differences in the setup, also outlined in [2], the software generally provide reasonable results that are consistent with each other. The initial stiffness is well aligned in all models and also the resistance values of most of the configurations are in agreement. Some exceptions are observed in the SREMB models for R1 and R2 cases (particularly with the low axial stress, 0.1 MPa), which tend to align with the residual resistances obtained from the other models. This is likely due to the cantilever beam assumption made for the piers, thus neglecting the coupling effect provided by the spandrel. For the unstrengthened t_0 3Muri analyses, both the models considering the Eurocode and the Italian guidelines are presented. The latter provide resistances more aligned with the other software, as they consider the coupling effect of the spandrel.

It is also reminded that in the R1 and R2 analyses with Midas GEN, the variation of the vertical load in single piers during the lateral loading does not affect their resistance.

The R1 and R2 analyses with PRO-SAP generally provide higher resistances than the others, when low vertical stresses are considered.

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.0

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_1.0_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_1.0_t1	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_1.0_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_1.0_t1	
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_1.0_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_1.0_t1	
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.5

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_1.5_t0	Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_1.5_t1	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa	0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 70) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 40). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 70) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 40). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	
Capacity curve R1:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 250) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 250) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	
Capacity curve R2:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: blue (highest capacity), green (middle), and yellow (lowest capacity). All curves show a peak followed by a drop and then a secondary peak.</p>	

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_1.5_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_1.5_t1
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa
Capacity curve URM:			
Capacity curve R1:			
Capacity curve R2:			

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_1.5_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_1.5_t1
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa
Capacity curve URM:			
Capacity curve R1:			
Capacity curve R2:			

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_0.8

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_0.8_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_01_1.2_0.8_t1
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa
Capacity curve URM:			
Capacity curve R1:			
Capacity curve R2:			

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_0.8_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_03_1.2_0.8_t1
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa
Capacity curve URM:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 150) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 45). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~115 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=30 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~135 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=30 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~70 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=30 mm.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 150) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 45). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~130 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=35 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~140 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=35 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~110 kN at d=5 mm and drops to 0 at d=35 mm.</p>	
Capacity curve R1:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~260 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=45 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~200 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=65 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~180 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=65 mm.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~260 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=75 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~220 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=65 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~190 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=65 mm.</p>	
Capacity curve R2:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for LP (t0). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 350) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 120). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~310 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=45 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~290 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=60 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~250 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=60 mm.</p>	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for PP5 (t1). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 350) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 120). Three curves are shown: a solid blue line, a dashed green line, and a solid yellow line. The blue curve reaches a peak of ~310 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=75 mm. The green curve reaches a peak of ~310 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=60 mm. The yellow curve reaches a peak of ~270 kN at d=10 mm and drops to 0 at d=60 mm.</p>	

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_0.8_t0		Portalframe_L5.2_05_1.2_0.8_t1
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa
Capacity curve URM:			
Capacity curve R1:			
Capacity curve R2:			

2.2. Single story walls

Single story walls representing a symmetric wall with two window openings are analysed; the main features are summarized in Figure 2.2.

ID: "Single story wall A_B_C":

- A is for the total height;
 - B is for the pier aspect ratio: e.g. $1a$ for 1.0;
 - C is for the axial stress on piers (additionally to the self-weight): 01-03-05 for 0.1, 0.3 or 0.5 MPa, respectively.
- t_1 configuration (spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie, resistance 100 kN), is considered

Figure 2.2 Single-story walls (measures in mm)

The results are gathered in three different tables, provided in the following, which differ in the magnitude of the axial load (additional to the self-weight) applied to the piers (0.1-0.3-0.5 MPa). In each table, the curves on the left refer to the 3.35 m tall wall, and those on the right to the 3.85 m tall one.

The resistances of the 3.85 m tall wall result generally higher than those of the 3.35 m one under the same configuration assumptions (URM, R1 or R2).

Similar conclusions as for the Portal frame in §2.1 can be drawn, with results reasonably consistent with each other, considering the intrinsic differences in the models. The initial stiffness is well aligned and the resistances are generally in good agreement (with exception for the SREMB models for R1 and R2 cases with low axial stress); displacement capacities look also quite similar.

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1a

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1a_01		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1a_01	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1a_03		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1a_03	
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1a_05		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1a_05	
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1b

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1b_01		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1b_01	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1b_03		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1b_03	
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for LP (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 50). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 120-150 kN at approximately 5 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 20-30 mm displacement.</p>		<p>Graph showing Capacity curve URM for PP5 (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 300) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 50). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 170-190 kN at approximately 5 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 20-30 mm displacement.</p>	
Capacity curve R1:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for LP (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 400) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 220-250 kN at approximately 10 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 40-50 mm displacement.</p>		<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R1 for PP5 (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 400) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 300-330 kN at approximately 10 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 40-50 mm displacement.</p>	
Capacity curve R2:	<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for LP (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 500) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 300-320 kN at approximately 10 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 40-50 mm displacement.</p>		<p>Graph showing Capacity curve R2 for PP5 (0.3 MPa). The y-axis is V [kN] (0 to 500) and the x-axis is d [mm] (0 to 100). Multiple curves (solid and dashed lines in various colors) show a peak load around 400-420 kN at approximately 10 mm displacement, followed by a plateau and then a sharp drop-off after 40-50 mm displacement.</p>	

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1b_05		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1b_05	
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1c

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1c_01		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1c_01	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1c_03		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1c_03	
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Singlestorywall_h3.35_1c_05		Singlestorywall_h3.85_1c_05	
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:	<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for URM. Y-axis 0-160, X-axis 0-40. Curves for LP (blue), PP3 (green), and PP5 (yellow) show peak forces around 100-110 kN at d ≈ 5 mm.</p>		<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for URM. Y-axis 0-160, X-axis 0-40. Curves for PP3 (green), PP5 (yellow), and SREMB (magenta) show peak forces around 130-140 kN at d ≈ 5 mm.</p>	
Capacity curve R1:	<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for R1. Y-axis 0-250, X-axis 0-70. Curves for LP (blue), PP3 (green), and PP5 (yellow) show peak forces around 160-170 kN at d ≈ 10 mm.</p>		<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for R1. Y-axis 0-250, X-axis 0-70. Curves for PP3 (green), PP5 (yellow), and SREMB (magenta) show peak forces around 190-200 kN at d ≈ 10 mm.</p>	
Capacity curve R2:	<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for R2. Y-axis 0-300, X-axis 0-80. Curves for LP (blue), PP3 (green), and PP5 (yellow) show peak forces around 200-210 kN at d ≈ 10 mm.</p>		<p>Graph showing shear force V [kN] vs displacement d [mm] for R2. Y-axis 0-300, X-axis 0-80. Curves for PP3 (green), PP5 (yellow), and SREMB (magenta) show peak forces around 240-250 kN at d ≈ 10 mm.</p>	

2.3. Two story walls

Two-story walls representing the walls of a building with different opening configurations are analysed; the main features are summarized in Figure 2.3.

ID: "Two-story wall_A_B_C":

- A is for the total height;
 - B is for the opening configuration (a: left picture, b: right picture)
 - C is for the axial stress applied on the piers at the upper floor (additionally to the self-weight): 01-03-05 for 0.1, 0.3 or 0.5 MPa, respectively.
- t_1 configuration (spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie, resistance 100 kN), is considered

Figure 2.3 Two-story walls (measures in mm)

The results are gathered in three different tables, provided in the following, which differ in the magnitude of the axial load (additional to the self-weight) applied at the top of the upper floor piers (0.1-0.3-0.5 MPa). In each table, the curves on the left refer to the a-wall configuration, and those on the right to the b-wall one.

To make consistent comparisons, the results of the SREMB models refer to displacements evaluated at the top of the structure. Such displacements are obtained by adding to the displacements calculated for the critical story (the ground floor), as specified in REPORT 2.1 [2], the elastic displacement of the upper floor (for which a cantilever behavior is considered for the piers).

The capacity curves still remain in very good alignment in terms of initial stiffness across all configurations. However, already in the URM configurations, noticeable differences in terms of resistance emerge: the Midas GEN resistances generally represent the upper limit, while the PRO-SAP ones the lower limit. The 3Muri values range between these two for the lower axial stress, although showing lower resistances than PRO-SAP at higher axial loads. The lower values in the 3Muri software are due to the collapse of the spandrels before the complete formation of the plastic hinges in the base piers.

In the reinforced (R1 and R2) simulations in 3Muri of the Two-storywall_h6_b, the total base shear in the direction from the squat 1st story pier to the slender pier is lower, because the software considers the pier at the base that is subject to vertical stress reduction, to be in tension and therefore does not contribute to the total base shear.

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Two-storywall_h6_a_01		Two-storywall_h6_b_01	
Axial stress:	0.1 MPa		0.1 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Two-storywall_h6_a_03		Two-storywall_h6_b_03	
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa		0.3 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Two-storywall_h6_a_05		Two-storywall_h6_b_05	
Axial stress:	0.5 MPa		0.5 MPa	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

2.4. Pilot building

The analysed pilot building has in plane dimensions of 5750x4350 mm² and the height of 6000 mm. The main dimensions are summarized in Figure 2.4 . The structure features four two-story bearing walls, an intermediate floor and a plane roof acting as rigid diaphragms. The total loads of the intermediate story and roof are 73.5 kN and 52.4 kN, respectively, and are supported by the East and West walls. Fixed supports are assigned at the base, simulating a stiff foundation. Spandrel configuration *t1* is considered (spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie, resistance 100 kN).

Figure 2.4 Pilot building walls (measures in mm)

The results are gathered in a table provided in the following: the curves on the left refer to the longitudinal loading direction (X, North-South) and those on the right to the transversal one (Y, East-West).

To make consistent comparison, the results of the SREMB models refer to displacements evaluated at the top of the structure. Such displacements are obtained by adding to the displacement of the critical storey (the ground floor), as specified in REPORT 2.1 [2], the elastic displacement of the upper floor (for which a cantilever behavior is considered for the piers).

The agreement in terms of initial stiffness is excellent among all the models and for both loading directions.

In URM configurations, resistance values are also in quite good alignment for the X direction, while more scattered in the Y direction. In particular, results seem noticeably affected by the lateral load distribution assumed for Midas GEN and 3Muri, with the highest values coming from the load distribution proportional to masses, and the lowest from the distribution proportional to the fundamental mode shape (which is also the one adopted by PRO-SAP models). However, such differences tend to decrease when moving from URM to R1 and R2.

3Muri models tend to underestimate the displacement capacity of the structure in the X direction, due to a shear collapse of the central pier in the West wall, that precedes the bending mechanism, since the resistances of the two mechanisms are comparable.

In the 3Muri R1-Y simulations, the initial resistance peak is due to the shear hinge formation in the spandrels of the East wall and the formation of the bending hinge in the base pier that is subject to vertical stress reduction.

In the 3Muri R1-X simulations, the shear resistance of the two central piers is slightly lower than the bending resistance, also because 3Muri considers the reduction coefficient of 0.8 on the shear resistance of the CRM, so they fail in shear and the deformation capacity is approximately halved. The same occurs in R2.

The SREMB results are generally comparable, although the displacement capacities look quite overestimated in the Y direction.

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5	PP5
ID:	Pilot_building_X		Pilot_building_Y	
Capacity curve URM:				
Capacity curve R1:				
Capacity curve R2:				

2.5. Benchmark building

The benchmark building is a small two-story primary school and consists of a main elongated rectangular block (dimensions 31x11 m²), and an adjacent annex, along the longer side (approx. 15x4.5 m²). Main technical drawings are reported below (Figure 2.5 and 2.6). The main block is articulated into three large rooms (classrooms) at the front side and a corridor at the back. The annex is divided into three functionally independent parts, with the central one housing the staircase.

The two storeys are identical in terms of dimensions and wall characteristics. The inter-storey height is 5.31 m; the load-bearing walls are mainly composed of 0.4 m thick, coursed stone masonry (a); exceptions for the spine wall of the main block and the external walls of the right part of the annex, made of 0.25 thick solid brick masonry (b).

The intermediate floor slabs are of different types: timber (1.1), ribbed reinforced concrete slab with hollow clay infill (1.2), and reinforced concrete slabs (1.3 and 1.4). The roof of the main block consists of a ribbed reinforced concrete slab with hollow clay infill, completed with masonry wallets and hollow clay tiles, covered with tiles (2.1). Conversely, the annex is covered with reinforced concrete slabs and waterproofing membrane (2.2).

The material properties used in the modelling are summarized in REPORT 2.1 [1].

The intermediate floor and roof are assumed to perform as rigid diaphragms. Spandrels provided with an effective horizontal tie ($H_p = 90.6$ kN) are considered.

Figure 2.5 Reference building plans (measures in cm)

Figure 2.6 Reference building perspective views (measures in m)

The global view of the model is illustrated in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7 Reference building perspective views (measures in m)

The results are gathered in a table provided in the following: the curves on the left refer to the longitudinal loading direction (X) and those on the right to the transversal one (Y). In addition to this case study, a configuration involving the strengthening of the perimeter walls only (denoted as **R1p**) was also simulated to represent a minimally invasive intervention.

The agreement in terms of initial stiffness is excellent among all the models and for both loading directions. In all configurations, resistance values are also in quite good alignment for the both directions among different software.

In the **URM** configuration, in the X direction, collapse is governed by the diagonal shear failure of most spandrels in the longitudinal walls. Then, the piers develop bending damage and progressively collapse, with bending failure involving both storeys. In the Y direction, collapse is instead governed by shear failure of the transversal walls, mainly localized at the ground floor.

In the **R1** configuration, under X-direction loading the spandrels of the inner longitudinal wall fail due to a diagonal shear mechanism, while the piers of the outer longitudinal walls develop bending damage and progressively collapse, involving both storeys. Under Y-direction loading, collapse is governed by shear failure of the transversal walls, mainly localized at the ground floor in the MIDAS Gen and 3Muri software, whereas in PRO-SAP collapse localizes at the second storey.

In the **R1p** configuration, under X-direction loading diagonal shear failure initially affects the spandrels of the unstrengthened inner longitudinal wall and subsequently propagates to the spandrels of the strengthened perimeter walls. The piers of the inner wall reach bending failure, whereas only bending damage develops in the piers of the perimeter walls. Under Y-direction loading, collapse is first governed by shear failure of the unstrengthened inner transversal walls

and subsequently by shear failure of the strengthened outer transversal walls; in both cases, damage is predominantly concentrated at the ground floor in MIDAS Gen and 3Muri. By contrast, when loads are distributed according to the principal mode in the Y direction, PRO-SAP localizes collapse at the second storey due to shear failure of the outer transversal walls.

In the **R2** configuration, under X-direction loading diagonal shear failure occurs in the spandrels of the inner longitudinal wall, whereas the piers of the outer longitudinal walls develop bending damage and progressively collapse, affecting both storeys. Under Y-direction loading, collapse is again governed by shear failure of the transversal walls, with damage mainly concentrated at the ground floor.

Software:	Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4
Ref. partner:	LP	PP3	PP5
ID:	Pilot_building_X		Pilot_building_Y
Capacity curve URM:			
Capacity curve R1:			
Capacity curve R1p:			

3. Comparisons with simplified analytical models

It is useful to compare the numerical results obtained from the different software in §2 with some simplified analytical predictions, in order to assess their reliability for quickly evaluating the current seismic vulnerability of the structure and for rapidly pre-designing the strengthening intervention.

The analytical evaluations are based on the correlations calibrated in the “PRO-SIS” Report 1.1 [3], which assume that the in-plane behavior of piers is governed by the weakest failure mechanism, either flexural or diagonal cracking.

Examples of the application of this analytical approach to the portal frames, single- and double-story walls previously analysed in §2.1-2.3 are herein provided. Specifically, the global capacity curves are given for comparison.

To obtain the analytic curves, the simplified, elastic-plastic capacity curve of each pier is calculated first (i.e. stiffness, resistance, failure mode, elastic limit and ultimate displacements). Subsequently, the curves of all the piers are combined, by summing the ordinates, to obtain the global capacity curve of the structure. The global ultimate displacement is considered to be reached when the first pier attains its ultimate limit drift.

However, the resistance of a pier in a structure (and, in particular, the bending resistance), is strictly related to the entity of the coupling effect provided by the adjacent spandrels, which is very complex to determine a priori. Thus, two different calculations are performed for each pier, using both cantilever (*ct*) and shear-type (*st*) static schemes. The cantilever and shear-type static schemes determine the lowest and higher performance limits, respectively. The global capacity curve should actually fall within these extremes.

3.1. Portal frames

The analytical predicted resistance and ultimate displacement values for the portal frame (Figure 3.1), are presented in Table 3.1 and compared with the numerical results in Figure 3.2 (for t_0 configuration) and Figure 3.3 (for t_1). Thick curves refer to the analytic model.

The results obtained from the numerical simulations, even though showing some variation, generally tend to fall within the range of the analytically predicted values. Stiffness and resistance analytic values of the shear type configurations, that represent the higher limits, are rarely exceeded by the numerical curves. It also generally emerges that, in the transition from URM to R1 and then R2 configurations, the numerical curves tend to get closer to the cantilever analytic configurations. It is also observed that, as the spandrel aspect ratio increases, the curves progressively approach the cantilever analytical configuration.

ID: "L5.2_A_1.2_1.0_B":

- L5.2 is the total wall width in meters;
- A is for the axial stress on the piers: 01-03-05 for 0.1-0.3-0.5 MPa;
- 1.2 is the length of the spandrel;
- 1.0 is the spandrel aspect ratio;
- B is for the spandrel configuration: t_1 or t_0 . t_1 is spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie (resistance 100 kN), t_0 is spandrel without any horizontal tie.

Figure 3.1 Portal frame (measures in mm)

Table 3.1 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.0 (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]	Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]
URM	0.1	F	33.4	28.9	F	66.7	28.9
	0.3	F	93.0	28.9	D	167.4	14.5
	0.5	F	143.3	28.9	D	202.3	14.5
R1	0.1	F	96.7	57.9	F	193.3	57.9
	0.3	F	150.0	57.9	F	299.9	57.9
	0.5	F	195.7	57.9	D	357.1	28.9
R2	0.1	F	152.8	57.9	F	305.6	57.9
	0.3	F	199.2	57.9	F	398.4	57.9
	0.5	F	238.5	57.9	F	477.1	57.9

Table 3.2 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.5 (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]	Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]
URM	0.1	F	35.0	27.6	F	70.0	27.6
	0.3	F	97.6	27.6	D	175.7	13.8
	0.5	F	150.4	27.6	D	212.3	13.8
R1	0.1	F	101.4	55.2	F	202.9	55.2
	0.3	F	157.4	55.2	F	314.7	55.2
	0.5	F	205.4	55.2	D	367.1	27.6
R2	0.1	F	160.4	55.2	F	320.7	55.2
	0.3	F	209.1	55.2	F	418.1	55.2
	0.5	F	250.3	55.2	F	500.7	55.2

Table 3.3 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Portal frame L5.2_1.2_0.8 (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]	Failure mode	V [kN]	d_u [mm]
URM	0.1	F	32.5	29.7	F	65.1	29.7
	0.3	F	90.7	29.7	D	163.2	14.9
	0.5	F	139.7	29.7	D	197.2	14.9
R1	0.1	F	94.2	59.4	F	188.4	59.4
	0.3	F	146.2	59.4	F	292.4	59.4
	0.5	F	190.8	59.4	D	352.1	26.7
R2	0.1	F	149.0	59.4	F	298.0	59.4
	0.3	F	194.2	59.4	F	388.4	59.4
	0.5	F	232.5	59.4	F	465.1	59.4

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.0

Figure 3.2 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_1.0_t0

Figure 3.3 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_1.0_t1

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_1.5

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.4 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_1.5_{t0}

0.1 MPa_t1

0.3 MPa_t1

0.5 MPa_t1

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.5 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_1.5_t1

- Portal frame L5.2_1.2_0.8

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
---------------------	------------------	------------------	-------

Figure 3.6 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_0.8_t0

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.7 Analytic-numeric comparison, for portal frame L5.2_A_1.2_0.8_t1

3.2. Single story walls

- The analytical predicted resistance and ultimate displacement values for the single story walls (Figure 3.8), are presented in Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1a

Table 3.4 and Table 3.5 and compared with the numerical results in Figure 3.9 (Single-story wall_h3.35_1a) and Figure 3.10 (Single-story wall_h3.85_1a). Thick curves refer to the analytic model.

The numerical curves never exceed both stiffness and resistance analytic values of the shear type configurations. For the 3.35 m tall wall, the numeric curves come very close to the cantilever analytic configurations, while for the 3.85 m tall wall, the numeric curves are generally slightly higher.

ID: "Single story wall A_B_C":

- A is for the total height;
 - B is for the pier aspect ratio: e.g 1a for 1.0;
 - C is for the axial stress on piers (additionally to the self-weight): 01-03-05 for 0.1, 0.3 or 0.5 MPa, respectively.
- t_1 configuration (spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie, resistance 100 kN), is considered

Figure 3.8 Single-story walls (measures in mm)

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1a

Table 3.4 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.35_1a (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	103.1	24.4	F	206.2	24.4
	0.3	F	243.8	24.4	D	417.6	12.2
	0.5	F	361.7	24.4	D	499.5	12.2
R1	0.1	F	255.7	48.9	F	511.3	48.9
	0.3	F	381.4	48.9	D	698.2	24.4
	0.5	F	488.9	48.9	D	780.1	24.4
R2	0.1	F	390.4	48.9	F	780.9	48.9
	0.3	F	499.3	48.9	D	978.9	24.4
	0.5	F	591.2	48.9	D	1060.8	24.4

Table 3.5 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.85_1a (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	127.1	30.3	F	254.2	30.3
	0.3	F	292.5	30.3	D	496.3	15.2
	0.5	F	431.0	30.3	D	592.5	15.2
R1	0.1	F	307.3	61.4	F	614.5	61.4
	0.3	F	455.0	61.4	D	825.4	30.3
	0.5	F	581.3	61.4	D	921.6	30.3
R2	0.1	F	466.1	61.4	F	932.2	61.4
	0.3	F	594.0	61.4	D	1154.4	30.3
	0.5	F	701.7	61.4	D	1250.6	30.3

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.9 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.35_1a

Figure 3.10 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.85_1a

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1b

Table 3.6 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.35_1b (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	43.5	19.8	F	87.0	19.8
	0.3	F	102.3	19.8	F	185.9	19.8
	0.5	F	151.5	19.8	F	222.3	19.8
R1	0.1	F	107.3	39.6	F	214.6	39.6
	0.3	F	159.8	39.6	F	319.6	39.6
	0.5	F	204.7	39.6	D	394.6	19.8
R2	0.1	F	163.6	39.6	F	327.2	39.6
	0.3	F	209.1	39.6	F	418.2	39.6
	0.5	F	247.4	39.6	F	494.8	39.6

Table 3.7 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.85_1b (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	51.3	22.2	F	102.7	22.2
	0.3	F	116.4	22.2	D	206.5	11.1
	0.5	F	170.8	22.2	D	246.3	11.1
R1	0.1	F	122.4	44.3	F	244.8	44.3
	0.3	F	180.5	44.3	F	361.0	44.3
	0.5	F	230.1	44.3	D	436.0	22.2
R2	0.1	F	184.9	44.3	F	369.8	44.3
	0.3	F	235.2	44.3	F	470.3	44.3
	0.5	F	277.5	44.3	F	555.0	44.3

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.11 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.35_1b

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.12 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.85_1b

- Singlestorywall_h3.35/3.85_1c

Table 3.8 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.35_1c (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	23.1	18.0	F	46.3	18.0
	0.3	F	54.0	18.0	F	108.1	18.0
	0.5	F	79.9	18.0	D	152.6	9.0
R1	0.1	F	56.7	35.9	F	113.4	35.9
	0.3	F	84.3	35.9	F	168.6	35.9
	0.5	F	107.9	35.9	F	215.8	35.9
R2	0.1	F	83.6	35.9	F	172.6	35.9
	0.3	F	110.2	35.9	F	220.4	35.9
	0.5	F	130.4	35.9	F	260.7	35.9

Table 3.9 Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Single-story walls_h3.85_1c (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	26.0	19.3	F	52.1	19.3
	0.3	F	57.8	19.3	F	115.6	9.6
	0.5	F	84.4	19.3	D	161.4	9.6
R1	0.1	F	60.9	38.5	F	121.8	38.5
	0.3	F	89.3	38.5	F	178.6	38.5
	0.5	F	113.5	38.5	F	227.1	38.5
R2	0.1	F	91.5	38.5	F	183.0	38.5
	0.3	F	116.1	38.5	F	232.1	38.5
	0.5	F	136.7	38.5	F	273.4	38.5

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3	PRO-SAP v24.10.0	3Muri v.12.6.2.4	SREMB
---------------------	------------------	------------------	-------

Figure 3.13 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.35_1c

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

3Muri v.12.6.2.4

SREMB

Figure 3.14 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Single-story wall_3.85_1c

3.3. Two-story walls

The analytical predicted resistance and ultimate displacement values for the two-story walls (Figure 3.15), are presented in Table 3.10 and Table 3.11, and compared with the numerical results in Figure 3.16 (Two-story wall_h6_a) and Figure 3.17 (Two-story wall_h6_b). Thick curves refer to the analytic model.

It is observed that the calculations refer to the ground floor, where the failure is expected, due to the higher lateral load. However, to make consistent comparisons with the numerical curves, the analytic displacements are evaluated at the top of the structure. Such displacements are obtained by adding to the displacements calculated for the ground floor, the elastic displacement of the upper floor (for which a shear type or a cantilever behavior is considered, coherently with the assumption made for the ground floor). The ultimate displacement is set at the attainment of the central pier collapse of the ground floor.

As expected, the numerical curves never exceed both stiffness and resistance analytic values of the shear type configurations. The numerical curves generally fall within the range of the two analytic curves, in terms of both stiffness and resistance. Also, the ultimate displacements of the wall_b, evaluated analytically, are aligned with the numerical values; differently, in the wall_a, the numerical displacements tend sometimes to widely exceed the analytical values. Actually, the numerical models detect in some cases the failure of the spandrels (Report 2.1 [2]), which leads to the activation of a global collapse mechanism (throughout the entire height of the building).

ID: "Two-story wall_A_B_C":

- A is for the total height;
- B is for the opening configuration (a: left picture, b: right picture)
- C is for the axial stress applied on the piers at the upper floor (additionally to the self-weight): 01-03-05 for 0.1, 0.3 or 0.5 MPa, respectively.

t_1 configuration (spandrel provided with an effective horizontal steel tie, resistance 100 kN), is considered

Figure 3.15 Two-story walls (measures in mm)

Table 3.10: Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Twostorywall_h6_1a (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	48.4	18.8	F	96.9	18.8
	0.3	F	79.7	18.8	F, D, F	142.9	8.9
	0.5	F	110.0	18.8	D	176.0	8.9
R1	0.1	F	85.2	37.7	F	170.3	37.7
	0.3	F, D, F	117.8	18.8	F, D, F	233.0	18.8
	0.5	F, D, F	145.4	18.8	F, D, F	273.1	18.8
R2	0.1	F	121.7	41.1	F	243.5	41.1
	0.3	F	149.6	41.1	F	299.3	41.1
	0.5	F	172.8	41.1	F	345.7	41.1

Table 3.11: Analytical resistance (V) and ultimate displacement (d_u) for the Twostorywall_h6_1b (σ_0 = axial stress, F = flexural failure; D = diagonal cracking failure).

	σ_0 , [MPa]	Cantilever			Shear type		
		Failure mode	V_{ct} [kN]	$d_{u,ct}$ [mm]	Failure mode	V_{st} [kN]	d_{st} [mm]
URM	0.1	F	47.5	20.5	F	94.9	20.5
	0.3	F	113.0	20.5	F, D, D	184.2	10.3
	0.5	F	139.4	20.5	D	227.8	10.3
R1	0.1	F	85.4	41.1	F	170.9	41.1
	0.3	F	123.9	41.1	F	247.7	41.1
	0.5	F	153.5	41.1	F, D, F	306.5	20.5
R2	0.1	F	118.5	41.1	F	237.1	41.1
	0.3	F	151.3	41.1	F	302.5	41.1
	0.5	F	175.6	41.1	F	351.2	41.1

Figure 3.16 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Two-story wall_h6_a

Figure 3.17 Analytic-numeric comparison, for Two-story wall_h6_b

4. Comparisons with detail numerical models

It is useful to compare the numerical results obtained from the different software in §2 with some detailed numerical simulations based on refined Finite Element Models (FEM), with the aim of assessing the reliability of the simplified simulations in reproducing the seismic vulnerability of the structure and the effects of the strengthening intervention.

Specifically, the refined numerical results obtained with the software OOFEM, broadly discussed in Report 1.3 [5], are herein considered for comparison, referring to the benchmark following examples:

- Single-story wall_3.85_1c_03 (Figure 4.1a)
- Two-story wall_h6_a_03 (Figure 4.1b) and Two-story wall_h6_b_03 (Figure 4.1c);
- Pilot building (Figure 4.1d).

The capacity curves for the simplified and advanced numerical models are compared in Figure 4.2 for the single-story wall, in Figure 4.3 for the two-story walls, and in Figure 4.4 for the pilot building (considering the longitudinal loading direction (X+, South-to-North)). Note that the advanced numerical curves of the pilot building refer to the configuration with unconnected transversal walls, as reported in [5]. Thick curves in the graphs refer to the OOFEM detailed model.

Figure 4.1 Single-story wall_3.85_1c_03 (a), Two-story wall_h6_a_03 (b) and _h6_b_03 (c), and pilot building walls (d)

Looking at the comparisons, it generally emerges that the simplified models well capture the stiffness of the refined models, but tend to slightly underestimate the resistance and, more significantly, the ultimate displacement.

A reasonable justification relies primarily in the different resistance model assumed for the masonry bending failure. Actually, in the simplified models, the masonry tensile strength is neglected and a conventional ultimate drift limit (taken from [6]) is set, which is conservative compared to the experimental evidence.

It should also be noted that the ultimate drift limits adopted in the simplified numerical simulations for the strengthened configurations have been prudentially set lower than the experimental ones (see [3]). Furthermore, once the ultimate drift values are attained, a sudden element collapse has been considered, neglecting any residual resistance (which actually emerged experimentally and is considered by the detailed model).

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3

PRO-SAP v24.10.0

Figure 4.2 Simplified/advanced-numerical models' comparison, for Single-story wall_3.85_1c_03

Two-story wall_h6_a_03

Two-story wall_h6_b_03

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3 **PRO-SAP v24.10.0** **3Muri v.12.6.2.4** **SREMB**

Figure 4.3 Simplified/advanced-numerical models' comparison, for Two-story wall_h6_a_03 and l_h6_b_03

Midas Gen 2024 v1.3 **PRO-SAP v24.10.0** **3Muri v.12.6.2.4** **SREMB**

Figure 4.4 Simplified/advanced-numerical models' comparison, for the pilot building

Acknowledgments

The PRO-SIS project is funded by the Interreg VI-A Italy-Slovenia Programme 2021-2027, co-funded by the European Union.

All the project partners that actively contributed to the project are gratefully acknowledged.

References

- [1] Gattesco N et al. 2025. "PRO-SIS Report 1.4: Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation software".
- [2] Gattesco N et al. 2025. "PRO-SIS Report 2.1: Results of the analyses on various existing masonry buildings with the procedures of WP1".
- [3] Gattesco N et al. 2024. "PRO-SIS Report 1.1: Design analytical models".
- [4] Gattesco N et al. 2025. "PRO-SIS Report 1.2: Numerical models for simulating the behavior of reinforced elements/buildings".
- [5] Gattesco N et al. 2025. "PRO-SIS Report 1.3: Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings".
- [6] Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti, Circolare 21 gennaio 2019, n. 7, "Indicazioni per l'applicazione delle Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni di cui al Decreto Ministeriale 17 gennaio 2018", C.S.LL.PP, 2019.
- [7] Magenes G, Calvi GM. 1997. "In-plane seismic response of brick masonry walls". Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics, 26: 1091-1112.